

INNOVATIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ANTHROPOCENTRIC PROVERBS AND ITS MEANS IN EXPRESSING THOUGHTS

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Annotation. The issue of anthropocentric proverbs is discussed in the article from the perspectives of comparative linguistics, language theory, and non-native language teaching techniques. In order to determine the similarities and differences between the studied and native languages, proverbs a type of paremiological cliché and the focal point of the universal and national cultural heritage are analyzed from the perspective of lingua contrast. The stages of introducing it into the educational process are proposed to be carried out while taking into consideration the theoretically possible and present in the students' speech interference in the target language as a result of contact in their minds of the features of two languages when teaching proverbs of a non-native language (English or Russian), developing a system of educational and language tasks, and doing so.

Keywords: proverb; anthropocentrism; native language; non-native language; interference; learning tasks; individual; society.

Introduction. Speech interference affects the analysis of proverbs on all linguistic levels (sound, lexical, word formation, morphological, syntactic, and stylistic). Nonetheless, due to the proverb's figurativeness, aesthetic elevation, and mobility of meaning, semantic errors are common. There are similarities and variations between anthropocentric proverbs in the studied (Russian or English) and native (Turkic) languages.

The main variations are in the methods by that anthropocentricity is communicated, such as the lexical variety used to denote the concept of a person, the frequency with which nominal speech particles are used, etc. A proverb, as a carrier of a distributor, a treasure trove of folk wisdom with an anthropocentric orientation is studied in many ways. Anthropocentrism in language and methodology implies the functioning of a person in the world of language and language in the world of man in all spheres of activity of the individual and society - from everyday life to official relationships within the

state and between states, as well as in all systems of education, science, and upbringing.^[1]

The anthropocentric paradigm of scientific knowledge brings to the fore a person and his language in the aggregate, which forms this scientific and at the same time educational paradigm in the minds of the individual and society, as an educational, scientific, educational, and cultural system of knowledge, skills, which are the basic life activity in various social spheres of society, in various life situations. Anthropocentrism is present in proverbs, sayings, phraseological units, rubaiyat, and didactic sayings, i.e. in all types of paremiological units. The presence of anthropocentrism in proverbs can be expressed explicitly and implicitly. For example Russian language: Баба с возу — кобыле легче. (explicitly). Без труда не вынуть рыбку из пруда. (implicitly). Uzbek language: Йигитни сўзи отадан, қизнинг сўзи онадан (explicitly: the speech of the young man from the father, the speech of the daughter from the mother). Ишласанг тишлайсан. ((implicitly: if you work, you will eat, that is, you will be full). English language: Like father, like son. (explicitly: like a father, like a son). A house is not a home. (implicitly: a house is not a house, i.e. a house is not just a building, or structure, but a place where a person lives, a family, or people close to you live).

Anthropocentric proverbs occupy a special place in the system of paremiological units of the language since they are aimed at a person, his activity, character, etc. directly, figuratively, abstractly, generalized, and collectively. The world of proverbs in general and anthropocentric proverbs, in particular, is the world of wisdom, experience, culture, history, folklore, and national mentality. At the same time, two content plans function in proverbs:

- 1) Universal (universal).
- 2) national-cultural (specific).

The universal (universal) aspect of proverbs shows that all mankind, regardless of national, linguistic, historical, cultural, and mental differences in general, has something in common that is inherent in all peoples of the world. For example, in the proverbs about labor: labor is a universal property, and diligence is characteristic of all peoples of the world. The national-cultural (specific) aspect in such proverbs is expressed in the characteristics of labor, in the ways of its implementation:

¹ Abbasova, N. K. (2018). Using Effective Techniques Developing Learners' Critical Thinking in Teaching English Proverbs and Sayings. Eastern European Scientific Journal, (6).

- for some people, this is fishing and related varieties of labor, tools, time, and place of labor;
- for other peoples, this is cattle breeding and the corresponding types of labor, place, methods of grazing, etc.

The difference in the features of labor activity, and therefore, in the corresponding customs, traditions, symbols, in speech turns with specific vocabulary, reflecting the inner and outer world of the ethnos and its individual, on the one hand, attracts foreigners to the study of a non-native language, and on the other hand, makes it difficult. This educational process is a culture of other nationality, which in general gives rise to speech interference and, in particular, semantic-stylistic and lingua-cultural interference. For example, Russian anthropocentric proverb Husband and wife are one Satan. In the Turkic-speaking audience, which still has a poor command of the Russian language, the meaning of the proverb can cause bewilderment and even form a negative attitude towards the concept of family, husband, and wife in the Russian sense. Most proverbs and sayings consist of two rhyming components. They convey morals in a literal and symbolic sense. Proverbs and sayings can be used in foreign language education to develop and regulate a wide range of communicative skills and abilities, including lexical and grammatical, speaking and writing, reading and listening, as well as their memorization, interpretation, and application in speech. While teaching proverbs and sayings in English classes, you can accomplish a variety of didactic purposes, including:

- teaching: strengthening students' translation abilities, enhancing their vocabulary, and boosting students' pronunciation and pronunciation skills.
- developing: expanding their horizons, acquiring the ability to communicate in a foreign language, and engaging their cognitive processes.
- educational: developing moral and ethical standards, encouraging tolerance for the customs and cultures of other people.
- motivating: creating and fostering long-lasting motivation, fostering the development of pupils' cognitive skills, and generating interest in learning a foreign language through reading the original language.

It should be emphasized that the usage of proverbs is crucial for the development of pronunciation abilities because pronunciation is the main emphasis of foreign language instruction from the very first classes. Proverbs

will be used in the class to help the teacher practice the pronunciation of each sound in a laid-back and enjoyable fashion at the start of the course.^[2]

Conclusion. The anthropocentric paradigm covers both theoretical and methodological aspects not only of the science of language but also of other sciences since it is characterized by interdisciplinarity, which is associated primarily with the activity functioning of a person in all areas of the social hierarchy of modern society. Language, as a conductor, a toolkit of culture used by an individual for communication, communication, and influence, is the semantic and structural base of all types of communications that are carried out through linguistic units - sounds, words, phrases, sentences and paremiological clichés (proverbs, sayings, phraseological units, etc.). The proverb, as a paremiological cliché, is studied from different scientific positions, which are based on different methodological approaches, which leads specialists to different types and types of its classification. In one of these classifications of proverbs, there is a typology of anthropocentric proverbs, in which a person is put at the forefront, which is expressed explicitly or implicitly in proverbs. Anthropocentric proverbs are studied both from the position of the theory of language, comparative linguistics, and from the position of linguodidactics and methods of teaching native and non-native languages. Anthropocentric proverbs of a non-native language are described based on the results of a comparative study with the native language of students, which allows for a scientifically based selection of educational and language material and the most realistic presentation of them in a system of exercises built taking into account the static and dynamic features of the two languages.

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